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“I HOPE YOU WERE A BAD MOM”

I hope you were a bad mom—
so that when no one wanted to pick me,
you didn't either.

I hope you were selfish,
so when it was time to leave,
you had the courage to walk away.

I hope you were harsh,
so you could let all the things that hurt you out.
Why didn't you say anything, Ma?

I hope you were greedy,
so that when all we had
was a pinch of powdered milk during Typhoon Yolanda,
you didn't still give it to the neighbor.
How could you give,
when it was already drought, Ma?

I hope you were honest,
so you didn't have to pretend it was fine
to let me carry that sack of rice
because your back was bent from scoliosis.

I hope you put yourself first instead of your children,
so you wouldn't have to lie
that you didn't like spaghetti, cake, or fruit—
all the food you wrapped in plastic
from your boss's birthday
and handed to us
like it didn't hurt to give it all away.

I hope you nagged—nagged so loud, so bad—
that you didn't have to carry everything in silence.
Why did you stay so quiet, Ma?

Didn't you know you grew a tumor from that?

I hope you had the audacity
to love yourself first,
so you wouldn't have to tie string to your slippers
just to make them last the walk to work,
so your hands could hold lotion
instead of callouses.

I hope you were an atheist,
so I wouldn't sit here questioning God—
wondering how a woman
with no money and so much faith,
who served the church with her whole heart,
could be taken so harshly.

I hope you knew how to talk back to your parents,
so when they said you'd stop at Grade 6
because you were "meant to serve everybody,"
you said no.
You said not me.

I hope you were ugly,
and difficult to deal with—
because, as they say,
bad people live long.

I hope you didn't choose to be kind to everybody,
so your funeral wouldn't be visited
by hundreds of butterflies,
while everyone whispered
that maybe they were heaven-sent.

So, please...
if the Lord decides you'll be reincarnated—
please choose to live a life for you.

Or if we could redo it all,
just be a bad mom.

Walk away when it's difficult.
I will be okay.

Just go and live the life you were meant to live.
Dress nicely.
Go places.
Dream higher.

Be an achiever—
all the things you told us to be.

But please...
be a bad mom a little more—
so we could spend time with you
a little longer.

